

Eco-Friendly Sonochemical Synthesis of Biologically Important Bis-5,5-dimethyl-1,3-cyclohexanedione Derivatives in Recyclable Triethylammonium Acetate (TEAA) Ionic Liquid

Dhruva Kumar¹, Rajesh Kumar², Hardeep Singh³, Gagandeep Singh⁴

¹Department of Chemistry, Guru Nanak College, Budhlada-151502, Mansa, Punjab, India

²Department of Chemistry, Government Degree College Khundian, District Kangra- 176030, HP, India

^{3&4}Department of Physics, Guru Nanak College, Budhlada-151502, Mansa, Punjab, India

Article History

Received: 18/08/2023

Accepted: 25/09/2023

Article ID: RRBB/13

Corresponding Author:

E-Mail: ohm23dhruva@gmail.com

Abstract

An efficient and environmentally friendly method has been developed for the synthesis of bis-5,5-dimethyl-1,3-cyclohexanedione derivatives (arylmethylene bis-dimedones) using triethylammonium acetate (TEAA) ionic liquid under ultrasound irradiation. The reaction of aromatic aldehydes with dimedone proceeds through Knoevenagel condensation followed by Michael addition, giving high yields in short reaction times. TEAA acts as a recyclable green solvent, while ultrasonication provides an eco-friendly energy source, making the process simple, mild, and efficient.

Keywords: Triethylammonium acetate (TEAA), Dimedone (5,5-dimethyl-1,3-cyclohexanedione), aromatic aldehydes, Sonochemical, bis-5,5-dimethyl-1,3-cyclohexanedione.

Introduction

The synthesis of bis-5,5-dimethyl-1,3-cyclohexanedione derivatives, commonly known as arylmethylene bis-dimedone compounds, has attracted considerable attention due to their various importance as intermediates in organic synthesis and medicinal chemistry.¹ Derivatives of 1,3-cyclohexanedione have been widely applied organic synthesis and in the preparation of pharmaceuticals, agrochemicals, and highly biologically active compounds, including herbicides, anticancer agents, antiviral agents, and enzyme inhibitors.²⁻⁶ Generally

these compounds have been synthesized through the condensation of aromatic aldehydes and dimedone (5,5-dimethyl-1,3-cyclohexanedione) via a Knoevenagel condensation followed by Michael addition.^{4,7} Over the past few decades, numerous catalysts and reaction conditions have been employed for the synthesis of bis-5,5-dimethyl-1,3-cyclohexanedione and its derivatives that include solid acids, metal salts, metal oxides, surfactants, silica sulfuric acid, KF/Al₂O₃, heteropoly acids and various organic catalysts.⁸⁻¹⁰ Although many methods have been developed, several of

them suffer from limitations such as long reaction times, use of toxic solvents, high temperatures, or expensive catalysts.

In recent years, significant progress has been made toward green and sustainable synthesis. In this context important development have been made in the use of ionic liquids as alternative solvents due to their low vapor pressure, high thermal stability, and recyclability.¹¹⁻¹² Because of

these advantages, they are considered environmentally benign alternatives to traditional volatile organic solvents. Various ionic liquids have been successfully applied in many organic transformations, among them; triethylammonium acetate (TEAA) has attracted greater interest due to its low cost, easy preparation, and reusability. A comparison of triethylammonium acetate (TEAA) is given here in Table 1.

Table 1. Advantages of TEAA over other catalysts & reaction conditions.

Catalyst	Limitations	Advantage of TEAA
Mineral acids	Corrosive and non-recyclable	TEAA is mild and reusable
Metal catalysts	Expensive and toxic	TEAA is metal-free
Solid acids	Difficult separation	TEAA is easily recyclable
Organic solvents	Volatile and hazardous	TEAA is non-volatile
Conventional heating	Long reaction time	Ultrasound + TEAA accelerates reaction

In addition to green solvents, sonochemistry has emerged as an effective technique for enhancing organic reactions considered as a green source of energy.¹³⁻¹⁴ Sonochemical reactions typically show advantages such as shorter reaction times, higher product yields, improved selectivity, and milder reaction conditions compared with conventional heating methods.

In continuation of efforts toward sustainable organic synthesis, we report a green sonochemical method for the synthesis of bis-5,5-dimethyl-1,3-cyclohexanedione derivatives using triethylammonium acetate (TEAA) as an economical and recyclable ionic liquid. This method combines ionic liquid media with ultrasonic activation and offers several advantages such as mild

reaction conditions, short reaction times, simple work-up, and very high yields, making it an environmentally friendly alternative to previously reported methods.^{8-10, 15}

Experimental

Melting points were measured in open capillary tubes and are reported without correction. All reagent-grade chemicals were obtained from commercial suppliers and used directly without additional purification. Ultrasound irradiation was carried out using a laboratory ultrasonic bath operating at 40 kHz. Infrared (IR) spectra were recorded as KBr pellets on a Perkin-Elmer 240C analyzer. ¹H NMR spectra were obtained on a Varian Gemini 300 spectrometer operating

at 300 MHz, with tetramethylsilane (TMS) used as the internal reference standard. The progress of the reactions was monitored by thin-layer chromatography (TLC) using silica gel G plates from Merck.

Typical procedure of triethylammonium ionic liquid (TEAA) synthesis¹⁶

The synthesis of the ionic liquid was carried out in a 250 cm³ RBF equipped with a reflux condenser and immersed in a water bath. Acetic acid (1.5 mol, 90.1 g, 86.03 cm³) was added dropwise to triethylamine (1.0 mol, 101.2 g, 139.4 cm³) at 70 °C over a period of 1.0 h. After the completion of the addition, the reaction mixture was stirred at 80 °C for 2 h to ensure completion of the reaction. The resulting mixture was then dried at 80 °C under high vacuum (5 mm Hg) until a constant weight was obtained. The ionic liquid triethylammonium acetate (TEAA) was obtained in 96% yield.

General Procedure for the Synthesis of Bis-5,5-dimethyl-1,3-cyclohexanediones:

A mixture of an aromatic aldehyde (1.0 mmol), dimedone (5,5-dimethyl-1,3-cyclohexanedione) (2.0 mmol), and triethylammonium acetate (TEAA) (3.0 mL) was subjected to ultrasound irradiation at 60 °C for an appropriate time (Table 2). The progress of the reaction was monitored by thin-layer chromatography (TLC). After completion, the reaction mixture was poured into distilled water (10 mL). The precipitated solid was filtered, washed with water, and recrystallized from ethanol to afford pure bis-5,5-dimethyl-1,3-cyclohexanediones (bis-dimedone derivatives) (**3a-h**).

Ionic Liquid Recycling: The mother liquor containing TEAA was subjected to

distillation at 80 °C under reduced pressure (5 mm Hg) for 2 h to remove water, leaving behind the ionic liquid. The recovered TEAA was reused in subsequent reactions without significant loss of activity, and the conversion and yield remained unchanged even after five cycles.

Results and Discussion

A mixture of benzaldehyde (1.0 mmol) and dimedone (2.0 mmol) in TEAA ionic liquid was sonicated at 60 °C (Scheme 1, product 3a). After aqueous work-up, bis-5,5-dimethyl-1,3-cyclohexanedione was obtained in 96% yield within 25 min (Table 2). The reaction progress was monitored by TLC. Prolonging the reaction time up to 60 min did not lead to any significant change in the yield.

The reaction proceeds through Knoevenagel condensation followed by Michael addition, affording bis-5,5-dimethyl-1,3-cyclohexanedione derivatives (Scheme 1). Encouraged by this result, the method was extended to a variety of aromatic aldehydes. As shown in Table 2, the procedure is generally applicable to a wide range of substituted aromatic aldehydes. Substituents on the benzaldehyde ring had little effect on the reaction time or product yield.

The ionic liquid TEAA was successfully recycled and reused up to five times without noticeable loss of its activity or yield in the reaction of aromatic aldehydes with dimedone (Scheme 1). TEAA is an air- and water-stable ionic liquid that is easy to prepare and relatively inexpensive, making it an attractive and practical medium for green organic synthesis.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of Bis-5,5-dimethyl-1,3-cyclohexanedione Derivatives Using Ultrasound Irradiation and TEAA.

Table 2. Synthesis of Bis-5,5-dimethyl-1,3-cyclohexanedione Derivatives Using Ultrasound Irradiation and TEAA.

S.N.	R	Product	Time in min	Yield ^a	M.P. (°C)
1	H	3a	25	96	192–193
2	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	3b	40	92	168–170
3	2-Cl	3c	30	93	196–197
4	2,4-Cl ₂	3d	25	95	187–188
5	4-F	3e	35	88	184–185
6	3,4-OCH ₂ O	3f	40	86	165–166
7	4-Cl	3g	35	93	143–144
8	3,4-Cl ₂	3h	25	96	167–168

^aThe products were characterized by comparison of their melting points and spectral (IR, ¹H NMR) data with those of authentic samples.

bis(5,5-dimethyl-3-hydroxy-1-oxa-2-cyclohexen-2-yl)phenylmethane 3a: ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 1.12 (s, 6H, 2CH₃), 1.18 (s, 6H, 2CH₃), 2.30–2.48 (m, 8H, 4CH₂), 5.53 (s, 1H, CH), 6.52–6.81 (m, 5H, ArH), 9.44 (s, 1H, OH), 11.61 (s, 1H, OH); IR (KBr): 3000–2505, 2951, 2874, 1650, 1586, 1370, 1260, 1240, 1165, 1073, 950, 829, 788 cm⁻¹.

bis(5,5-dimethyl-3-hydroxy-1-oxa-2-cyclohexen-2-yl)-2-chlorophenylmethane (3c): ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 1.06 (s, 6H, 2CH₃), 1.17 (s, 6H, 2CH₃), 2.25–2.51 (m, 8H, 4CH₂), 5.63 (s, 1H, CH), 7.09–7.39 (m, 4H, ArH), 9.76 (s, 1H, OH), 11.88 (s, 1H, OH); IR (KBr): 3000–2500, 2955, 2929,

1611, 1470, 1380, 1289, 1230, 1140, 1070, 987, 743 cm⁻¹.

bis(5,5-dimethyl-3-hydroxy-1-oxa-2-cyclohexen-2-yl)benzo(3,4)dioxol-5-ylmethane 3f: ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 1.06 (s, 6H, 2CH₃), 1.24 (s, 6H, 2CH₃), 2.37–2.50 (m, 8H, 4CH₂), 5.44 (s, 1H, CH), 5.88 (s, 2H, OCH₂O), 6.49–7.06 (m, 3H, ArH), 9.70 (s, 1H, OH), 11.89 (s, 1H, OH); IR (KBr): 3000–2500, 2954, 2878, 1604, 1480, 1370, 1302, 1250, 1230, 1040, 940, 860, 812 cm⁻¹.

CONCLUSION

In summary, a simple, efficient, and environmentally friendly method has been developed for the synthesis of bis-5,5-

dimethyl-1,3-cyclohexanedione derivatives using triethylammonium acetate (TEAA) under ultrasound irradiation. The protocol affords high yields in short reaction times under mild conditions and is applicable to a wide range of aromatic aldehydes. Moreover, the ionic liquid can be recycled several times without significant loss of efficiency. The combination of TEAA and ultrasonic activation offers a green, economical, and operationally simple approach for the synthesis of bis-5,5-dimethyl-1,3-cyclohexanedione derivatives.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors are thankful to the Sophisticated Analytical Instrument Facility (SAIF), Central Instrument Laboratory, Panjab University, Chandigarh, for providing spectral analysis support. The authors also express their sincere thanks to Guru Nanak College Budhlada for their assistance and facilities.

REFERENCES

1. Hassan, E.; Abo-Bakr, A.; Fandy, R. 1,3-Cyclohexanedione and Its Derivatives as Precursors. *Int. J. Curr. Res.* **2014**, *6*, 9583–9637.
2. Horning, E. C.; Horning, M. G. Condensation Reactions of 1,3-Cyclohexanedione Derivatives. *J. Org. Chem.* **1946**, *11*, 95–99.
3. Nagarajan, K.; Shenony, S. J. Studies on 1,3-Cyclohexanedione Derivatives. *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B* **1992**, *31B*, 73–76.
4. Tu, S. J.; Gao, Y.; Liu, X. H.; Tang, S. F.; Qiu, X. J. Synthesis of Functionalized Cyclohexanedione Derivatives. *Chin. J. Org. Chem.* **2001**, *21*, 1164–1167.
5. Tu, S. J.; Zhou, J. F.; Lu, Z. S.; Deng, X.; Shi, D. Q.; Wang, S. H. Efficient Synthesis of Bis-Dimedone Compounds. *Synth. Commun.* **2002**, *32*, 3063–3068.
6. Poupelin, J. P.; Saint-Rut, G.; Foussard-Blanpin, O.; Narcisse, G.; Uchida-Ernouf, G.; Lacroix, R. Synthesis and Biological Activity of Cyclohexanedione Derivatives. *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* **1978**, *13*, 67–71.
7. Kidwai, M.; Saxena, S.; Khan, M. K. R.; Thukral, S. S. Aqua-Mediated Synthesis of Bis-Dimedone Derivatives Catalyzed by p-TSA. *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* **2005**, *40*, 816–819.
8. Jin, T.-S.; Wang, A.-Q.; Ma, H.; Zhang, J.-S.; Li, T.-S. The Reaction of Aromatic Aldehydes and 5,5-Dimethyl-1,3-Cyclohexanedione under Solvent-Free Grinding Conditions. *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B* **2006**, *45*, 470–474.
9. Heravi, M. M.; Bakhtiari, K.; Oskooie, H. A.; Taheri, S. Efficient Synthesis of Arylmethylene Bis(dimedone) Derivatives Catalyzed by Heteropoly Acids. *J. Mol. Catal. A: Chem.* **2007**, *263*, 279–281.
10. Wang, L.; Sheng, J.; Zhang, L.; Han, J.; Fan, Z. Efficient Synthesis of Arylmethylene Bis(dimedone) Derivatives Using ZnO Catalyst. *Chin. Chem. Lett.* **2010**, *21*, 686–689.
11. Welton, T. Room-Temperature Ionic Liquids: Solvents for Synthesis and

- Catalysis. *Chem. Rev.* **1999**, *99*, 2071–2084.
12. Rogers, R. D.; Seddon, K. R. Ionic Liquids—Solvents of the Future? *Science* **2003**, *302*, 792–793.
13. Mason, T. J.; Lorimer, J. P. Applied Sonochemistry: Uses of Power Ultrasound in Chemistry and Processing. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2002**, *31*, 289–297.
14. (a) Suslick, K. S. Sonochemistry. *Science* **1990**, *247*, 1439–1445. (b) Li, J.-T.; Li, Y.-W.; Song, Y.-L.; Chen, G.-F. Improved Synthesis of 2,2'-Arylmethylene bis(3-hydroxy-5,5-dimethyl-2-cyclohexene-1-one) Derivatives Catalyzed by Urea under Ultrasound. *Ultrasonics Sonochemistry* **2012**, *19*, 1–4.
15. Khan, K. M.; Maharvi, G. M.; Khan, M. T. H.; Shaikh, A. J.; Perveen, S.; Begum, S.; Choudhary, M. I. Tetraketones: A New Class of Tyrosinase Inhibitors. *Bioorg. Med. Chem.* **2006**, *14*, 344–351.
16. Greaves, T. L.; Drummond, C. J. Protic Ionic Liquids: Properties and Applications. *Chemical Reviews* **2008**, *108*, 206–237.